

Extended Essay Subject

Economics

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Evaluating government intervention to mitigate the Covid-stricken
Egyptian tourism industry

Research question

To what extent is government intervention effective in mitigating the
impacts of Covid-19 on the Egyptian touristic sector?

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Introduction

‘Tourism - an economic and social phenomenon’ (UNWTO, n.d.). As one may have discerned, the quotation cited falls under no defined time-period (n.d.) insinuating that tourism is a timeless marvel for which it does not span a fixed epoch. Over the decades, tourism has exponentially grown and diversified to become one of the most dominant, dynamic and fast-paced industries in the world (UNWTO, n.d.).

In essence, the tourism industry is amongst the most treasured sources of Egyptian national income, a significant contributor to the country’s gross domestic product (GDP), an indispensable source of foreign exchange earnings as well as a vital source of employment (K Elnagar & Derbali, 2020). However, the tourism industry has experienced a crippling shock by virtue of the detrimental pandemic that is Covid-19. The World Travel and Tourism Council’s annual Economic Impact Report (EIR) discloses that the dramatic fall of Egypt’s Travel and Tourism sector wiped out a stunning \$17.6 billion from the nation’s economy in 2020. Accordingly, the sector’s influence on GDP dropped by 55% - EGP505.6bn/ \$32.0bn in 2019 (8.8% of total economy), to EGP227.5bn/ \$14.4bn in 2020 (3.8% of total economy) (WTTC, 2021).

On the report of IFRPI, imitations of the economy utilizing the Social Accounting Matrix (SAM) multiplier model for Egypt (Figure 1) insinuates that for each month that Covid-19 persists national GDP could fall by between 0.7% and 0.8% (EGP36-41bn/ \$2.3-\$2.6bn). The absence of tourists solely is expected to cause monthly losses of EGP26.3 billion/ \$1.5 billion. Thus, the

projected loss in tourism revenues accounts for approximately two thirds of the total estimated impact (approximately 0.5% out of 0.8%) (Breisinger, Abdel Latif, Raouf, & Wiebelt, 2020).

Figure 1: Estimated GDP loss per month, less pessimistic and more pessimistic scenarios, percent of average 2019 monthly GDP

Figure 1. IFRPI Social Accounting Matrix (SAM) (Breisinger, Abdel Latif, Raouf, & Wiebelt, 2020)

Besides the ramifications entertained, it is imperative to acknowledge tourism’s contribution to domestic employment. The tourism sector formerly employed upwards of 2.4152 million workers representing 9.2% of total employment in Egypt. However, in light of recent times, the sector presently employs an underwhelming 1.5711 million workers; thus, total contribution of travel and tourism to employment declined by approximately a third (35%) triggering 844,100 job losses (WTTC, 2021). In turn, these job losses struck the entire travel and tourism sector predominantly SMEs (small and medium-sized enterprises) which constitute eight out of ten of all businesses in the sector (WTTC, 2021).

All statistics entertained do not account for vicissitudes in government policy. It is important to highlight that the Egyptian government has fulfilled no formal scheme to mitigate the impacts of Covid-19 on the tourism industry contrary to the Tourism Reform Program (launched in

November 2018) which outlined a novel tourism strategy (OECD, 2020). Rather, the government has enacted a cluster of random scattered reforms to fight the pandemic and its instantaneous, unpredictable ramifications. However, one must account for the unprecedented challenges Covid has introduced, thus making it difficult for policy makers to engineer appropriate policies.

All things considered, said unpredictable nature has induced me to explore the disorderly reforms legislated and their true effectiveness on the Egyptian touristic sector. Moreover, it is important to stress that there exist difficulties in measuring the impacts of Covid-19 on a micro-economic scale. Additionally, macro-economic indicators such as those previously entertained are not dependable (Vagliasindi, 2021), particularly when addressing the question **“To what extent is government intervention effective in mitigating the impacts of Covid-19 on the Egyptian touristic sector?”**.

Methodology

In assessing the extent to which government intervention has been effective in mitigating the impacts of Covid-19 on the tourism industry in Egypt, I first began by distinguishing legislation and regulation from alternative forms of government intervention undertaken at the micro-economic level; namely, wage subsidies and nudges. The reason behind such distinguishment is because legislation and regulation have supposedly devastated the industry in quest of preventing the viral spread in the short run; meanwhile, other interventions have presumably relieved/facilitated the economy. The economical question presents itself; how can said devastation be measured?

Firstly, one must acknowledge the covert complexity of touristic demand; such that tourism is not necessarily a good or service per se. Upon indulging in Larry Dwyer's 'Tourism economics and policy' - 2nd Edition, it has become translucent that there subsist two types of touristic demand. The first was actively measured by means of tourist arrival figures adapted from the UNWTO Database. A lifecycle was subsequently introduced and adapted in congruence with personally gathered legislative reforms. The second type of demand was inventively measured using inbound plane tickets sales. Subsequently, to confirm that said legislations and regulations are the sole trigger of the demand shock, the price elasticity of demand (PED) of plane tickets was justifiably calculated to determine the level of elasticity of 'tourism'. Owing to constrained data availability, an interview was conducted to collect absent price figures.

Having explored all facets of touristic demand, the preordained echo in supply was subsequently statistically and graphically tackled. Before all else, tourism's interconnectivity with the rest of the economy was addressed to correctly envisage the 'real' effect of said demand shock on the supply-side of the economy. Accordingly, it was disclosed that the fall in touristic expenditure had instigated numerous business closures, thus prompting mass layoffs, in addition an ordinary producer's standpoint was taken up to envisage the effects of the supply-shock on the market in the short and long run.

Henceforward, wage subsidies were examined as a tool enacted to battle the fall in touristic labor. To graph said wage subsidies each individual subsidy imbursed within (April 27 - October 29) was gathered and unified from a multitude of trusted news articles and accordingly dissected. Successively, the wage subsidies were graphed and evaluated. Similarly, CAC legislations and regulations as well as consumer nudges were gathered and analyzed to effect.

Measuring demand for travel to a destination

First and foremost, it is essential to acknowledge that there exist difficulties in measuring the demand for tourism since ‘tourism’ is not a good or service per se. Thus, it is important to differentiate between two types of demand: *demand for travel to a destination* and *demand for a specific touristic good or service* (Dwyer, Forsyth, & Dwyer, Tourism Economics and Policy, 2020). Preparatory to tackling the first type of demand; a certain model must first be familiarized to ease the process of measurement of demand; that is the pandemic lifecycle which consists of 5 timely stages; namely, emergence, proliferation, aggravation, recession, and recovery (ECES, 2020). For the ensuing text, the pandemic lifecycle will be of constant referral.

Figure 2. Pandemic lifecycle (ECES, 2020)

With regards to *demand for travel to a destination*; upon the **proliferation** of COVID in Egypt (March 19) (Figure 2), the state introduced legislations to internalize the externality of COVID, notably; suspension of all flights, lockdowns, curfews, etc. (Refer to Appendix 1). In turn, all

legislative precautions employed have induced a tremendous opportunity cost whereby in pursuit of public safety, said legislations and regulations have devastated the demand for tourism, especially the suspension of domestic and international flights in March which put tourism at an all-time halt; thus, causing a drop of approximately -57.7% MoM in tourist arrivals. However, the repercussions do not stop here as tourist arrivals fell by an inconceivable -100.0% in April (UNWTO, 2020) as the government extended the state of emergency and indefinitely tightened the suspension of international flights (Crisis24, 2020). The table below illustrates the demand for travel to Egypt by measuring the change in tourist arrivals on a yearly and monthly basis.

Month	Prior to the pandemic (2019)	Amid the pandemic (2020)	Percentage change (YoY)	Percentage change 2020 (MoM)
January	861	945	+9.8	-
February	885	942	+6.4	-0.32
March	1097	398	-63.7	-57.7
April	1220	1	-100.0	-100.0
May	932	2	-99.8	+100.0
June	1083	5	-99.5	+150.0
July	1225	89	-92.7	...
August	1221	223	-81.7	+150.6

Figure 3. International tourist arrivals to Egypt 2019/ 2020 ('000) (Adapted from UNWTO Tourism Dashboard & October 2020 Barometer/ Statistical Annex) (Refer to Appendix 2 & 3)

It is worth highlighting that the number of tourist arrivals increased upon the **emergence** of the virus (Stage 1) (Figure 2) - between Jan of 2019/ 2020 (+9.8%) as well as February of 2019/2020 (+6.4%) which is logical as the pandemic had not yet hit congruently Egypt was arguably on an

upwards trend in terms of performance afore the pandemic given all-time high grossing revenues (USD13.03bn) (Daily News Egypt, 2020). However, not long after tourist arrivals fell by -63.7% year on year (YoY) and -57.7% month on month (MoM), hence it was discernible that COVID-19 had hit tourism in March thus marking the **proliferation** of the virus (Stage 2). As previously stated, tourist arrivals fell by a staggering -100.0% in April as due to decisive governmental legislations (Refer to Appendix 1); thus, realizing the next stage of the lifecycle ‘**aggravation of the problem**’ (Stage 3). Nevertheless, one must acknowledge the greater change in percentage decrease (rate of decrease) across the years 2019/2020 (-100.0, -99.8, -99.5, ...) indicating recession (Stage 4) and more importantly the increase in tourist arrivals occurring on a monthly basis (1, 2, 5, 89, ...), the reason for this phenomenon is the enactment of decisive governmental intervention (to be entertained subsequently).

Measuring demand for a specific touristic good or service

With regards to *demand for a specific touristic good or service*, one good that can capture demand for tourism as a product is plane tickets given it is a good/ service typically consumed by the greater majority of tourists. According to the UNWTO ‘Arrivals by mode of transport’ analysis, 85.6% of international inbound tourist arrivals to Egypt are airborne (carried through commercial flight) (UNWTO, 2019). Using stratified sampling; let us take two samples of tourists who actively consume said good; alternatively stated, two countries who constitute the highest percentage of inbound arrivals to Egypt; namely, Germany and Saudi Arabia. In substance, Germany constituted 14% of inbound arrivals to Egypt in 2019 while Saudi Arabia constituted 7% whilst in 2020 Germany held steady at 14% while Saudi Arabia rose to 9% (WTTC, 2021). Figure 4 depicts ticket prices to Cairo from Jeddah in early 2020 (Q1- pre covid)

and late 2020 (Q3- amid covid). Moreover, it is assumed that the overall fall in demand for plane tickets (signified by tourist arrivals - Figure 2) is strictly influenced by non-price determinants; namely, the number of consumers (willing and able to buy plane tickets), seasonal changes, future expectations (instigated by the pandemic) as opposed to changes in price. However, plane tickets are an economic good and thus demand for them is to some extent influenced by changes in price. The extent to which a touristic good or service is influenced by non-price determinants and thus contributes to the extremity of the demand shock will be explored in the following section, where if proven to be price inelastic (relatively low responsiveness of demand to changes in price) (Tragakés, 2020), it'd be discernable that the pandemic is the sole trigger of the demand shock.

EgyptAir	Ticket price (August -2020)	Ticket price (January-2020)
From Saudi Arabia (Jeddah) to Egypt (Cairo)	2100 riyal	900 riyal

Figure 4. Inbound ticket prices (Adapted from an Admin Supervisor responsible for travel at a Saudi Arabian Multinational Organization)

With regards to tourism demand and price elasticity of demand (the extent to which demand for a touristic good or service changes given a change in its price) (Tragakés, 2020). Such calculation will shed light on the extent to which the change in price has impacted demand for travel as opposed to non-price determinants (arising from the pandemic).

The price elasticity of demand for airline tickets can be calculated as follows:

$$\epsilon = \frac{\text{Percentage change in the quantity demanded of plane tickets } (\% \Delta Q)}{\text{Percentage change in the price of plane tickets } (\% \Delta P)}$$

$$\epsilon = \frac{\frac{(223-945)}{945} * 100}{\frac{(2100-900)}{900} * 100} = |0.573|$$

The above data was adapted from Figure 2* and Figure 4*

The value above is less than one ($PED < 1$), indicating that the percentage change in quantity demanded is smaller than the percentage change in price; thus, the demand for plane tickets is price INELASTIC; thus, relatively low responsiveness to changes in price. Hence, it is evident that the decrease in demand for touristic goods or services; namely, plane tickets, are rather instigated by non-price determinants and not the increase in the cost of ticket prices. The extent to which the pandemic has impacted the tourism industry is justified as a PED value of -0.573 confirms the fact that the drop in tourist arrivals of -722,000 is independent of price changes since plane ticket are an economic good with few to no substitutes, once more asserting that it is not changes in price; rather, the severity of the pandemic that has triggered the demand shock.

Supply-shock in an interconnected economy

While it is evident that the pandemic took a toll beyond imaginable on the tourism industry; more precisely touristic demand, it has served as an opportunity to rethink how tourism interacts with the Egyptian economy. Predominantly, such a violent demand shock is bound to reverberate in the supply-side of tourism. Prior to visualizing the foreseen supply-shock, it is imperative to

take note of the domino effect and complementary goods to truly grasp tourism's interconnectivity with the Egyptian economy as well as the true repercussions of this shock.

Tourism is intertwined with countless other industries; namely, 1236 leading establishments (the breakdown is as follows: 442 agencies, 72 airlines, 178 car rentals and busses, 67 embassies, 24 hotel equipment and suppliers, 346 hotels and resorts, 92 restaurants, and 15 transportation) (Egypt Business Directory, n.d.). Dashan (Managing Director of OXCON and Fellow at Chatham House and TIMEP) claims "Overall, one out of every nine jobs in the country depends directly or indirectly on tourism" (Kamel, 2020). In addition, all listed industries produce goods which are complementary to those of the tourism industry thus the fall in quantity demand of say plane tickets gives rise to the fall in demand of all complements (two goods are complements if they tend to be used together). Thus, the direct effects of touristic expenditure fell on all suppliers who offer said goods and services directly to tourists. Below is a line graph extracted from CEIC Data illustrating the fluctuations in tourism receipts over the years (CEIC Data, n.d.).

Figure 5. Tourism receipts (CEIC Data, n.d.)

The time frame of interest is 2019-2020. According to the above illustrated graph Tourism receipts totaled to USD12.571bn in 2019 whilst in 2020 the value of receipts plummeted to USD9.859bn.

The percentage change of tourism receipts across said time frame is calculated as follows:

$$C = \frac{9.859 - 12.571}{12.571} \times 100 = -21.6\%$$

Hence it can be discerned that a drop of -21.6% occurred in tourism receipts across the years 2019/ 2020, indicating that with the fall in demand, so did supply, more precisely, market supply (the sum of the quantities supplied by each individual firm at each price). How does this observation translate graphically?

Figure 6. Demand for touristic goods and services

Figure 7. Supply of touristic goods and services

Quantity of Touristic goods and services (Q)

Quantity of Touristic goods and services (Q)

Figure 6 illustrates a decrease in demand; alternatively stated, a leftward shift of the demand curve from D1 to D2 due to a decrease in the number of consumers (tourist arrivals) and thus a decrease in touristic expenditure. Given the initial equilibrium (point A), there exists a fall in quantity demanded thus a shift to point B, point B is the point at which the quantity demanded of touristic goods and services is less than the quantity supplied, therefore the market is in a state of disequilibrium where excess supply is equal to the difference between points A and B. In application, the price of touristic goods and services did not instantaneously adjust owing to the abrupt drop in tourist arrivals hence inducing a delay whereby the price mechanism took time to function. However, downward pressure was later exerted causing the fall to point C, thus eliminating excess supply, and attaining a new equilibrium.

Nevertheless, this scenario did not endure, as supply correspondingly fell. Standard economic theory suggests that as price falls (refer to Figure 5, point C) producers are willing to supply less of the good or service (law of supply: as the price of a good or service increases, the quantity supplied increases and vice versa, *ceteris paribus*), thereby decreasing output and increasing price. This is seen in Figure 7, where the decrease in the number of touristic firms in the market; namely 25 hotels and 17 tourist restaurants (EgyptToday, 2020) as a result of the fall in tourist arrivals and thus touristic expenditure caused a sharp fall in supply, this is evident by the left shift of the supply curve from S1 to S2, triggering an increase in price; thus, attaining a new equilibrium at point D.

A producer's point of view

It is imperative that one closely examines a producer's standpoint/ perspective to fathom the true implications of the preordained supply shock on the market. Primarily, the tourism industry is an example of a monopolistically competitive market structure (Dwyer, Forsyth, & Dwyer, *Tourism Economics and Policy*, 2020) due to it virtually abiding by the ensuing characteristics, a large number of firms in the industry, no barriers to entry (thus firms are said to have freedom to entry) and the existence of product differentiation. As the name implies firms face some competition (as in perfect competition) yet also possess a certain degree of market power (as in perfect competition). Moreover, firms in monopolistic competition are subject to a demand curve that is less elastic than firms in perfect competition but more elastic than firms in monopoly. Figure 7 illustrates the market as it appears to you, meanwhile the ensuing figure illustrates the market as it appears to the ordinary producer.

Figure 8. Monopolistic competition Loss Graph (Tragakes, 2020)

The above figure illustrates the phenomenon of profit maximization by a firm in monopolistic competition the short run (the period of time when the firm has at least one fixed input). At the profit maximizing/ loss minimizing level of output $MC = MR$ (marginal revenue = marginal cost) the firm is seen to incur a loss (negative profit) whereby $AC > AR$ (average cost > average revenue) or $AC > P$; in monopolistic competition $P = AR = D$. Consequently, firms do not earn enough revenue to cover all their costs. However, in the long run (the period of time when the firm is able to vary all its inputs) firms may freely enter and leave the industry altogether thus justifying *the closure of the afore mentioned touristic firms*, causing the decrease in supply of touristic goods and services, subsequently driving price upwards (Figure 7).

Wage subsidies

The total or partial closure of tourism businesses; alternatively stated, the decrease in the number of touristic firms (fall in supply), triggered 844, 100 job losses instigated by mass layoff, collective redundancies and furloughing of workers. Despite the drastic increase in unemployment (35%) (WTTC, 2021), 1.5711 million tourism workers remain employed though are on the verge of unemployment due to reduction in salaries, or failure to meet basic wage. Thus, to tackle the problem and maintain/ protect existing labor, the ministry of manpower; more precisely, the employee's emergency fund 'the Fund' (the body responsible for supporting struggling firms to endure economic crisis and help fulfil obligations towards employees during such difficult times) (Riad&Riad, April) *initially* imbursed monetary subsidies to workers at 205 tourism establishments in Egypt (Daily News Egypt, 2020). Hence, the Fund aims at providing subsidies to employees who have not received basic wages from firms facing the risk of total or

partial closure due to economic crisis and thus preventing a lethal domino effect; decline in labor, decline in production of touristic goods and services, inability to achieve allocative efficiency and consequently market failure.

To further investigate the economic implications of the Fund, the concept of wage subsidies must first be entertained. Wage/ wage-related subsidies, first introduced by renowned economist Edmund Phelps, are disbursements to workers tied to the remuneration an employer pays an employee (Tabarrok, n.d.). Furthermore, wage subsidies are disbursed by the government through firms/ employers to employees and thus act to reduce or even eliminate the costs of labor to employers.

Concerning the Fund, the subsidy disbursed was divided into batches of sum equivalent to worker's salaries registered at the Social Insurance Authority. The minimum and maximum amounts are EGP600 and EGP1765, and the subsidy is equivalent to 100% of the workers basic wages (Egypt Today Staff, 2020). The table below (Figure 9) illustrates all subsidies disbursed to workers through firms within the time frame April 27-October 29.

Date	Amount	Accumulative Amount	Number of firms (public and private)	Number of workers	Batch
April 27, 2020	EGP 57m	EGP 57m	205	48,968	1
June 2, 2020	EGP 106m	EGP 163m	1,380	153,898	1
June 6, 2020	EGP 8m	EGP 171m	1,530	162,939	1
July 4, 2020	EGP 18.9m	EGP 189.9m	2,450	183,515	1
August 9, 2020	EGP 17.757m	EGP 207.657m	3,195	199,924	1
October 29, 2020	EGP 317.305m	EGP 317.305m	2,204	146,610	2 & 3

Figure 9. Wage subsidy distribution (Adapted from Daily News Egypt in correspondence with the Egyptian Minister of Manpower Mohamed Saafan)

In substance, the 1st batch of subsidies were disbursed over a period of 5 months – lasting between the 27th of April and the 9th of August. The first subsidy amounted to EGP57m and was disbursed to 48,968 workers at 205 firms (Daily News Egypt, 2020); meanwhile, the ensuing subsidy (imbursed on the 2nd of June 2020) was equivalent to approximately 85.96 % more (EGP106m) and was distributed to 104,930 workers at 1175 firms (Daily News Egypt, 2020) which is congruent with the governments recognition of more tourism workers (Daily News Egypt, 2020).

Conversely, EGP8m was disbursed the next month (June), though it was only disbursed to 9,041 workers at 150 firms (Daily News Egypt, 2020). On July 4, the government increased the subsidy imbursed (MoM) relative to the increase in number of workers. Finally on the 9th of

August the government disbursed a final EGP17.757m to 16, 409 workers (Daily News Egypt, 2020), amounting to 207.657m disbursed to 153,898 workers, thus settling the first batch of subsidies.

Moreover, the second and third batches are worth an approximate EGP317.05m disbursed to 146,610 workers at 2,204 firms (a 52.8% decrease on the first batch) (Daily News Egypt, 2020).

It is worth highlighting that the entirety of the subsidy is burdened by the government. Below is a graph illustrating the wage subsidy and its properties.

Figure 10. Wage Subsidy graph (Monthly)

The initial equilibrium is determined by the intersection of the market wage (w) and the quantity of labor (Q*). Thus, the market wage is assumed to be an average $((1765 + 600)/2)$, where 600 is the minimum basic wage and 1765 is the maximum basic wage, thus deriving the market wage at

point w. The highest point illustrated on the graph (r) is the maximum amount received by workers in which the government will subsidize. Hence, the wage wedge is calculated according to the highest amount in order to include all the amounts paid by the government to subsidize workers' wages (equivalent to 100% of the workers' wages (0-1765)). It is important to highlight that there exists no supply shift, where contrary to subsidies, wage/ wage-related subsidies aim to maintain existing labor (1.5711m workers) as opposed to increasing the quantity of labor in the market, thus the government have disbursed the subsidies to already registered workers. Thus, all figures calculated are grounded on the number of registered workers.

Nudges & CAC legislation and regulation

Recall the gradual monthly increase in tourist arrivals (Figure 3). Its covert causes will be explored in the subsequent/ ensuing section. On the 1st of July 2020, the Egyptian government gradually introduced CAC (command and control) legislation and regulation to drive demand (increase tourist arrivals), thus announcing the return and operation of international flights and tourist resorts (Crisis24, 2020). It is apparent that such legislation is extremely effective as tourist arrivals fell by 11% less on a yearly basis and increased by an astronomical 150.6% on a monthly basis. Moreover, the government eased COVID-19 restrictions for tourists; thus, obliging a single negative PCR test upon arrival (Africanews, 2021).

Likewise, in an effort to encourage more tourists to visit Egypt and to increase international spending, the Egyptian government dispersed nudges. Primarily, a nudge is a form of government intervention, designed to influence consumer's choices (tourists) in a predictable way, and to influence consumers to behave in socially desirable ways (Tragakes, 2020). One

nudge that the Egyptian government employed was the introduction of e-visas to tourists as an alternative to visas thus eliminating the hassles visas prompt. The e-visa supports 8 languages and addresses all tourists' inquiries. Furthermore, 46 nationalities were able to sign up for this visa, however now 74 nationalities can now obtain an e-visa (Marie, 2021).

Deputy prime minister of tourism and antiquities for tourism and antiquities Ghada claims that 'this update will encourage many tourists of different nationalities to visit Egypt' (Marie, 2021). As a matter of fact, since the enactment of said nudge in coordination with parallel nudges tourism has seen a spike in international tourist arrivals as indicated in Figure 3 whereby tourist arrivals increased from approximately 5,000 tourists in June to 89,000 tourists in July to 223,000 tourists in August.

Figure 11. Increase in demand in response to Nudges

The initial equilibrium illustrated in figure 11 is determined by point D (Figure 7). Following the enactment of said Nudges there occurs an increase in demand (tourist arrivals) alternatively stated a right shift of the demand curve by the quantity of touristic goods and services additional tourists demand thus attaining a new equilibrium at the intersection between the demand curve D2 and the supply curve S. Henceforth, illustrating how powerful nudges can be in driving demand and stimulating the tourism sector.

Conclusion

In response to the anticipated question **“To what extent is government intervention effective in mitigating the impacts of Covid-19 on the Egyptian touristic sector?”** Manifestly, government intervention initially devastated the touristic sector and in substance the impacts of Covid-19 were seen to reverberate across the entirety of the industry owing to the lethal domino effect. Thus, the enactment of momentous legislation was done at the cost of social benefit as opposed to economic or even socioeconomic benefit. This was seen though the measures of demand as well as comprehensive examination of the severe supply-shock. Following the containment of the spread, one may discern that government intervention drove tourism to restorable levels given; wage subsidies were enacted with the goal of maintaining existing labor meanwhile CAC legislation and regulation and nudges effectually stimulated the sector though pulsating it contrary to breathing new life into the sector and restoring it to its estimated levels afore the introduction of Covid-19. Looking forward, Egyptian governmental bodies should enhance measurement and statistical services allowing for more comprehensive quantification of micro-economic repercussions and perhaps better-prepare for any imminent calamities capable of posing critical threat to the Egyptian tourism industry, similar to Covid-19.

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Appendices

Appendix 1: Personally gathered governmental legislations and regulations adapted from Crisis24 - A Gardaworld Company newsletters

Precautions	Date	Stage
Country suspends all flights to and from china	January 27	-
First case of coronavirus confirmed in Egypt	February 14	-
EgyptAir to resume flights to China	February 20	1
EgyptAir delays resumption of flights to China	February 26	1
Governments implements entry restrictions for Qatari nationals	March 6	1
Health officials announce first Covid-19 fatality	March 8	1
Government suspends all flights	March 19-31	2
Government implements domestic restriction as Covid-19 spreads	March 19-31	2
All mosques and churches closed	March 21	2
Egypt authorities suspend international flights	March 19	2
Government to implement nighttime curfew	March 25	2
Several hospitals close temporarily for sterilization	March 29	2
Citizens to be quarantined upon arrival	March 31	2
Government to ban Ramadan gatherings due to COVID-19	April 7	2
Government extends nighttime curfew	April 8	2
Government extends nighttime curfew through Ramadan	April 23	2
Authorities extend state of emergency	April 28	3
Hotels to progressively begin operations	May 3	3
President ratifies amendments to emergency law	May 7	3
Mosques to remain closed as Ramadan ends	May 13	3
Authorities to tighten Covid-19 restrictions during Eid al-Fitr	May 24-29	3

Authorities indefinitely extend suspension of international flights	May 19	3
Egypt authorities announce Covid-19 curfew	May 30	3
Egypt authorities reduce curfew hours	May 31	3
International flights and tourist resorts to resume operations	July 1	4
Authorities record highest daily increase of Covid-19 cases to date	June 14	4
Authorities ease Covid-19 restrictions	June 24	4
National carrier announces resumption of flights	July 1	4
Over 85,000 Covid-19 cases reported	July 18	4
Authorities extend retail operating hours	July 26	4
Authorities warn of second Covid-19 wave as cases increase	August 12	4
Authorities to impose new entry restrictions	September 1	4

Appendix 2: UNWTO Tourism Dashboard, International Tourist Arrivals (Egypt 2019/ 2020)
(‘000) (UNWTO, 2020)

Appendix 3: October 2020 Barometer/ Statistical Annex (International Tourist Arrivals by Country of Destination) (UNWTO, 2020)

October 2020 – Statistical Annex

International Tourist Arrivals by Country of Destination																	
Rank '19 '18	Series	(million)			Change (%)		Series	Percentage change over same period of previous year									
		2017	2018	2019*	18/17	19*/18		2020*									
		YTD	Q1	Q2	H1	Apr.		May	Jun.	Jul.	Aug.	Sep.					
	World	1333	1408	1460	5.7	3.7		-70.1	-28.5	-94.9	-65.5	-97.1	-96.6	-91.5	-80.5	-78.6	
1	1 France	TF	86.9	89.4	..	2.9	..	TCE									
2	2 Spain	TF	81.9	82.8	83.7	1.1	1.1	TF	-73.0	-25.6	-99.1	-71.7	-100.0	-100.0	-97.7	-75.0	-75.9
3	3 United States	TF	77.2	79.7	79.3	3.3	-0.6	TF	-65.8	-18.3	-95.8	-60.1	-96.4	-95.9	-94.8	-93.1	
4	4 China	TF	60.7	62.9	65.7	3.6	4.5	TF	-84.1	-68.4	-98.1	-84.1	-98.9	-98.1	-97.3		
5	5 Italy	TF	58.3	61.6	64.5	5.7	4.8	TF	-59.3	-34.4	-81.4	-64.1	-90.3	-83.8	-72.4	-43.1	
6	6 Turkey	TF	37.6	45.8	51.2	21.7	11.9	TF	-76.5	-22.2	-97.9	-75.0	-99.3	-99.3	-96.0	-85.8	-70.9
7	7 Mexico	TF	39.3	41.3	45.0	5.1	9.0	TF	-47.2	-6.7	-75.9	-41.2	-78.5	-74.3	-74.8	-66.6	-62.2
8	10 Thailand	TF	35.6	38.2	39.8	7.3	4.2	TF	-77.3	-38.0	-100.0	-66.2	-100.0	-100.0	-100.0	-100.0	-100.0
9	8 Germany	TCE	37.5	38.9	39.6	3.8	1.8	TCE	-63.6	-25.0	-91.5	-64.3	-97.4	-95.3	-82.9	-61.2	
10	9 United Kingdom	TF	39.5	38.7	39.4	-2.2	1.9	VF	-16.1	-16.1							
11	11 Japan	VF	28.7	31.2	32.2	8.7	3.2	VF	-82.1	-51.1	-99.9	-76.3	-99.9	-99.9	-99.9	-99.9	-99.7
12	12 Austria	TCE	29.5	30.8	31.9	4.6	3.5	TCE	-44.0	-15.2	-88.9	-47.1	-99.3	-98.0	-76.2	-40.6	-35.5
13	13 Greece	TF	27.2	30.1	31.3	10.8	4.1	TF	-81.3	-15.2	-95.3	-78.8	-96.2	-97.7	-93.8	-85.4	
14	15 Malaysia	TF	25.9	25.8	26.1	-0.4	1.0	TF	-68.2	-36.8	-99.7	-68.2	-99.7	-99.7			
15	17 Portugal	TCE/TF	21.2	22.8	24.6	7.5	7.9	TCE	-65.7	-21.9	-98.2	-72.1	-99.3	-98.9	-96.4	-67.4	-39.9
16	16 Russian Federation	VF	24.4	24.6	24.4	0.7	-0.5	VF	-14.8	-14.8							
17	14 Hong Kong (China)	TF	27.9	29.3	23.8	4.9	-18.8	TF	-92.9	-83.5	-99.6	-91.2	-99.8	-99.7	-99.3	-99.1	-99.7
18	18 Canada	TF	20.9	21.1	22.1	1.2	4.8	TF	-79.1	-19.6	-98.3	-72.0	-98.3	-98.5	-98.2	-98.0	
19	19 Poland	TF	18.4	19.6	21.2	6.6	7.8	TF	-16.1	-16.1							
20	20 Netherlands	TCE	17.9	18.8	20.1	4.8	7.2	TCE	-58.9	-23.4	-86.9	-62.6	-98.3	-91.5	-70.8	-42.4	
21	21 Macao (China)	TF	17.3	18.5	18.6	7.2	0.8	TF	-87.3	-67.9	-99.5	-83.7	-99.6	-99.4	-99.4	-98.6	-95.8
22	26 Vietnam	VF	12.9	15.5	18.0	19.9	16.2	VF	-70.6	-18.1	-98.6	-55.8	-98.2	-98.3	-99.3	-98.9	-98.9
23	22 India	TF	15.5	17.4	17.9	12.1	2.8	TF	-53.5	-22.6	-100.0	-53.5	-100.0	-100.0			
25	27 Korea (ROK)	VF	13.3	15.3	17.5	15.1	14.0	VF	-80.2	-46.9	-97.9	-74.7	-98.2	-97.9	-97.5	-95.8	-95.7
26	24 Croatia	TCE	15.6	16.6	17.4	6.7	4.3	TCE	-63.8	-41.6	-86.4	-81.5	-99.9	-97.7	-76.0	-51.2	-52.9
27	23 Hungary	TF	15.8	17.2	16.9	8.7	-1.3	TF	-15.1	-15.1							
28	25 Utd Arab Emirates(2)	THS	15.8	15.9	16.7	0.8	5.1	THS(2)	4.1								
29	32 Indonesia	VF/TF	12.9	13.4	15.5	3.5	15.4	VF	-68.2	-30.6	-87.9	-60.0	-87.5	-86.9	-89.0	-89.2	-89.2
30	29 Singapore	TF	13.9	14.7	15.1	5.5	3.0	VF	-79.2	-43.3	-99.9	-71.4	-100.0	-99.9	-99.9	-99.6	-99.5
31	30 Czech Republic	TF	13.7	14.3	..	4.5	..	TCE	-67.5	-26.1	-95.7	-67.5	-99.8	-99.3	-88.5		
32	31 Ukraine	TF	14.4	14.2	..	-1.5	..	TF									
24	28 Saudi Arabia	TF	16.1	15.3	17.5	-4.8	14.3	TF	-65.2	-28.1	-98.2	-62.8	-98.3	-99.1	-96.1	-95.2	
33	33 Denmark	TF	12.4	12.7	13.3	2.6	4.2	TCE(1)	-69.2	-22.5	-92.8	-69.2	-97.0	-95.9	-87.5		
34	36 Egypt	VF	8.3	11.3	13.0	36.8	14.8	VF	-69.5	-19.6	-99.8	-62.3	-100.0	-99.8	-99.6	-92.8	-81.8